

Time-course moisture content studies and water diffusivity of wheat and corn seed

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Manuscript received 8 July 2002, revised 23 September 2002, accepted 16 December 2002

Time-course moisture content studies were conducted with wheat (PBW-343) and corn (Paras) seeds at 35°. The targeted moisture contents were 30, 35, 40 and 45% while single seed of each crop variety was used during the experiment. There were three replications and the results indicate that the targeted moisture contents are obtained after 10 h. The results for the integral diffusion coefficients ($\bar{D}$) indicate that there is a continuous decrease in $\bar{D}$ with time. The percent germination is maximum (90%) with 40% moisture content for wheat, whereas it is 100% for all the moisture contents in the case of the given corn seed.

The studies of the transport and uptake of water in germinating seeds are of prime importance¹. Water uptake in germinating seed occurs by diffusion phenomena and therefore for a complete understanding of the germination process a thorough knowledge of the phenomena is essential. We developed earlier a diffusion theory concerning electrolytes/non-electrolytes and a diffusion cell apparatus². Diffusion coefficients for a number of simple valence salts indicate that the seed membrane/coat acts as a very sensitive selective barrier for the transport of solute particles³. Keeping in view the importance of transport studies in germinating seed, an attempt was made to determine diffusion rates of water uptake by performing time-course moisture content studies in single wheat and corn seed at 35°, and diffusion coefficients were determined at different intervals of time by employing an empirical relation developed earlier⁵.

Results and discussion

Plots of moisture contents vs time, and $\bar{D}$ vs time for both the crop seeds are shown in Figs. 1 and 2, respectively. The results reveal that in both the seed varieties, the initial moisture content steeply increased initially with time, thereafter this trend somewhat decreased and at the duration of 10 h and beyond, it became constant, showing thereby that the seeds achieved nearly the desired targeted moisture contents at the above time period. It is surprising that for both the seed varieties, constancy in targeted moisture contents occurred at nearly 10 h and remained almost constant for the total duration of the experiment, i.e. 24 h. It is inferred that rather than sowing seeds after a lapse of ~24 h (which is the general practice after soaking the seeds), these varie-

Fig. 1. Plots of time-course moisture content of single seed of (a) wheat (PBW-343) and (b) maize (Paras) variety at 35°.

ties can be sown after 10 h when the targeted moisture contents are attained. Germination test was also conducted with fresh seeds (10 nos.), the initial moisture contents of which were raised to the targeted values by carrying out time-course moisture content experiments only for 10 h. The results indicated that for the wheat variety, percent germination obtained was 90% only for those seeds whose targeted moisture contents were raised to 40%, whereas in the case of corn variety this was 100% at all the four targeted moisture contents. viz. 30, 35, 40 and 45%.

Fig. 2. Plots of integral diffusion coefficient ($\bar{D}$) vs time of (a) wheat (PBW-343) and (b) maize (Paras) variety at 35°.

The data for average diffusion coefficients ($\bar{D}$) revealed that with the increase in the initial moisture content there was a continuous decrease in $\bar{D}$. Fig. 2 shows that during the first 4 h, there is a steep decrease in $\bar{D}$ for both the seed varieties, whereafter this trend is somewhat less marked upto 24 h when the diffusion rate is the minimum. This is expected and can be explained by the fact that during the initial period, water uptake by the seed is fast giving higher $\bar{D}$ values followed by slower uptake (lower $\bar{D}$) and finally very less absorption of water takes place for which $\bar{D}$ obtained is minimum.

Experimental

Wheat (PBW-343) and corn (Paras) seeds were procured from Department of Plant Breeding, Punjab Agricultural University, Ludhiana, India, and preserved in air-tight containers. Initial moisture contents in seeds were determined by a moisture meter. Wheat seeds with weight ranging from 0.04 to 0.05 g and corn seeds from 0.3 to 33 g were selected. Single seed was placed in a small air-tight plastic container and precalculated amount of water was added to achieve the desired targeted moisture content. There were three replications for each targeted moisture content and experiments were set-up after every 2 h upto 24 h in new containers. An air-thermostat (35 ± 0.1°) was employed. From the initial and final seed weights percent moisture contents were estimated. Due care was taken to keep the weight of seeds within the above stated range, and containers were also properly sealed in order to avoid any loss of water by evaporation. Pure water with a conductance of ~10⁻⁶ Ω⁻¹ was employed. The empirical relation employed for the determination of $\bar{D}$ from moisture contents is

$$\bar{D}\beta_{\text{seed}}t = \ln (MC_f - MC_i)$$

where, $\bar{D}$ is the integral diffusion coefficient, β_{seed} the seed constant, t the time of diffusion (s) and $(MC_f - MC_i)$ is the difference between final and initial moisture contents of the seed. β_{seed} determined by the procedure discussed elsewhere³, were found to be 61.3 × 10⁻³ and 233.03 × 10⁻³ for the varieties used of wheat and corn seed, respectively. The equation differs from that given by the theory²; that moisture contents are substituted in place of respective solute concentrations. This was necessary since during the time-course moisture content studies, the external amount of water diffused into the seeds, and the very basic driving force for diffusion phenomena, namely, a concentration (chemical potential) equalization process, becomes invalid. The values of $\bar{D}$ obtained from this new empirical relation, despite units of g cm² s⁻¹, would still provide a good estimate of the amount of water diffused into the seeds. This may be considered as a limitation of obtaining $\bar{D}$ in the usual units of cm² s⁻¹, but the approach nonetheless provides a reliable method for water uptake studies when moisture contents are taken into consideration.

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (M.L.S.) is thankful to Professor Alan G. Taylor, Cornell University, USA, for the training related to moisture content studies and to his wife Nishi for encouragement. Thanks are also due to Mrs. Poonam Verma for the moral support. The other author (A.P.) is

thankful to her husband, S. Rajeev Singh for encouragement.

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